

Tandem *N*-allylation/[3,3]-sigmatropic shift route to the synthesis of allyl ethers of dihydropyrimidines

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Abstract : We report herein the first instance of tandem *N*-allylation/[3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement of dihydropyrimidones leading to the facile synthesis of functionalized allyl ethers and thioallyl ethers of dihydropyrimidine wherein C=O and C=S form a part of [1,5]-hexadiene system necessary for [3,3]-sigmatropic shift.

Keywords : Tandem reaction, [3,3]-sigmatropic shifts, Biginelli reaction, *O*-allylation, *S*-allylation.

Introduction

Anionic oxy-Cope (AOC) rearrangement shares the defining characteristics of rapidly introducing molecular complexity from simple, easily obtainable starting material¹. This AOC technique has been elegantly used for the synthesis of many natural products². Previously, as the first instance, we have reported the participation π -bonds of naphthyl rings in Cope system³. Recently, we reported as the first instance where the π -bonds of two phenyl rings taking part in [3,3]-sigmatropic shift⁴. Further dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement of 1,2-dinaphthyl-1,2-diol of acyclic systems has been reported from our laboratory⁵. Synthesis of bicyclic ketones using diaromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement is also reported⁶. Depending upon the number of hetero atoms present in [1,5]-hexadiene system, Cope rearrangement is classified by Lutz as hetero-Cope, when one hetero atom is present and polyhetero-Cope, when two or more hetero atoms are present⁷.

We herein report the formation of *N*-alkyl dihydropyrimidones [DHPMs] from dihydropyrimidones which *in situ* undergoes [3,3]-sigmatropic shift leading to the formation of *O*-allyl and *S*-allyl ethers of dihydropyrimidones. In this [3,3]-sigmatropic shift there is a participation of C=S in a [1-*S*,3-*M*]-polyhetero Cope system and C=O in a [1-*O*,3-*M*]-polyhetero Cope system.

Dihydropyrimidones possess remarkable pharmacological activities such as antihypertensive, anticarcinogenic,

calcium channel blockers, neuropeptide Y (NPY) antagonists and analgesic agents⁸. Moreover, DHPM unit also present in the natural marine alkaloids batzelladine A and B which are found to inhibit the binding of HIV gp 120 to CD4 cells⁹. These DHPMs are usually synthesized by simple biginelli condensation¹⁰.

Results and discussion

We herein report an environmentally benign grindstone method for the synthesis of DHPMs (4, Table 1). This method involves grinding the synthons viz. ethyl

Table 1. Synthesis of dihydropyrimidones

Entry	4 ^a	R	X	Yield (%)
1	4a	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	S	94
2	4b	4-C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	S	89
3	4c	-C ₆ H ₅	S	88
4	4d	-C ₆ H ₅	O	92
5	4e	4-C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	O	89
6	4f	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	O	91

^aThe reaction was carried out on a 0.2 mmol scale, and the ratio of aldehyde : urea/thiourea : ethyl acetoacetate is 1 : 1.2 : 1.

acetoacetate or acetyl acetone, urea or thiourea and various aromatic aldehydes in the presence of catalytic amount of ortho phosphoric acid for about 30 min as shown in Scheme 1. The authenticity of the compounds prepared was confirmed by spectral data and comparing with the known compounds^{11,12}.

Scheme 1. Biginelli reaction.

The *N*-allylation of DHPMs was carried out using sodium hydride in dry THF under inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The characterization of the product obtained showed that the isolated product were not the expected *N*-allylDHPMs, but were allyl ethers of DHPMs (**5**, Table 2) as shown in Scheme 2.

Table 2. Formation of allyl ethers and thioallyl ethers

Entry	5 ^a	R	X	Yield (%)
1	5a	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	S	60
2	5b	4-C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	S	52
3	5c	-C ₆ H ₅	S	58
4	5d	-C ₆ H ₅	O	54
5	5e	4-C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	O	52
6	5f	4-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	O	53

^aThe reaction was carried out on a 0.2 mmol scale. The ratio of 4/NaH/allyl bromide is 1 : 1 : 1.2.

X-Ray single crystal structure of **5a**.

Crystal data for **5a** (Entry 1, Table 2) : C₁₈H₂₂N₂O₃S, *M* = 346.44, monoclinic, space group *C2/c*, *a* = 28.325 (5); *b* = 7.410 (2); *c* = 20.202 (4) Å, volume *U* =

Scheme 2. Tandem *N*-allylation/[3,3]-sigmatropic shift.

IR spectrum of **5a** (Table 2, Entry 1) showed the absence of C=S absorption. PMR spectrum showed doublet of doublet at δ 4.9 and 5.1 with *J* 9.6 Hz and 16.5 Hz respectively due to *cis* and *trans* allyl hydrogens. A doublet at δ 4.0 shows -S-CH₂ protons. Further HRMS showed *m/z* 346. The above spectral data enumerate the structure assigned as **5a**. Finally single crystal analysis confirmed the structure assigned for **5a** as follows¹³.

The structures for **5b**, **5c**, **5d**, **5e** and **5f** were assigned based on IR, PMR, ¹³C NMR and HRMS spectral data.

3610.9 Å³, *Z* = 8, μ = 0.197 mm⁻¹, 3183 unique reflections, 1.69 < θ < 25, *wR*₂ = 0.1251; *R*₁ = 0.0450 [*I* > 2 sigma (*I*)]. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (deg) for **5a** : C(1)-N(2) = 1.267(3); C(1)-N(1) = 1.387(3); C(1)-S(1) = 1.766(2); C(2)-N(2) = 1.486(2); C(2)-C(3) = 1.516(3); C(3)-C(4) = 1.360(3); C(3)-(C9) = 1.464(3); C(4)-N(1) = 1.387(3).

In order to ascertain the mechanism of formation *O*-allyl and *S*-allyl derivatives we repeated the reactions by stirring the reaction mixture for about half an hour instead of four hours. The products isolated were a mixture

of *N*-allyl dihydropyrimidone and allyl ether of dihydropyrimidone. *N*-Allyl dihydropyrimidone was separated using column chromatography as a yellow viscous liquid and characterized by spectral data. Therefore the formation of unexpected products (**5**) can be rationalized as a result of tandem *N*-allylation/[3,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement of DHPMs.

In conclusion, we propose a simple, facile and an efficient approach for the conversion of C=O and C=S of cyclic diimide and cyclic thiodiimide into *O*-allyl and *S*-allyl functionalities using tandem *N*-allylation/[3,3]-sigmatropic shift.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Reagent grade chemicals were purchased from commercial source and used as received. IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on a Bruker IR S66V analyzer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL GSX (400 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as a internal standard. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC run on silica gel G (Merck).

Typical experimental procedure for the synthesis of dihydropyrimidines :

A mixture of benzaldehyde (0.106 g, 1 mmol), ethyl acetoacetate (0.130 g, 1 mmol) and urea (0.070 g, 1.17 mmol) was ground with ortho phosphoric acid for about 30 min. The reaction mixture was cooled for 15 min and poured into a beaker containing 50 mL of cold water. The white solid obtained was filtered, washed with water (50 mL) and ethanol (5 mL). It was then recrystallized from ethanol (Yield : 0.26 g, 92%), m.p. 202–203 °C (lit.⁸ 201–202 °C). Selected spectroscopy data for **4d** : IR (KBr) 3230 (-NH str.), 3110 cm⁻¹ (-NH str.); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.2 (3H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz, CH₃-C-O), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃-C=C), 3.6 (2H, q, *J* 6.8 Hz, CH₂-O-C), 5.2 (1H, s, methine proton), 5.75 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchangeable), 6.8–7.2 (5H, m, ArH), 7.8 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchangeable).

Typical experimental procedure for the synthesis of allyl ethers :

To a suspension of NaH (0.100 g, 2 mmol, 50% dispersion in mineral oil washed with hexane) in dry THF (25 mL) a solution of DHPM, [(**4a**, Table 1, Entry 1) (0.594 g, 2 mmol) in dry THF (10 mL)] was added and stirred in an atmosphere of N₂ for one hour. Then a solution of allyl bromide (0.2 mL, 2.5 mmol) in dry THF

(5 mL) was added dropwise and stirred for further four hours (tlc control, silica gel, ethyl acetate : hexane 1 : 9 as eluent). Evaporation of solvent under reduced pressure gave a viscous solid which when chromatographed over a column of silica gel (eluent 1 : 10 ethyl acetate : hexane) gave a yellow solid (Yield : 0.42 g, 60%), m.p. 95–96 °C (recrystallized from methanol).

Selected spectroscopic data for 5a : Elemental analysis : Calcd. : C, 62.40; H, 6.40; N, 8.09(%); Found : C, 62.48; H, 6.31; N, 8.14(%); IR (KBr) 3312 (-NH str.), 1683 (C=O str., ester), 1478 (C=C, aliphatic), 1270 cm⁻¹ (-C-O-C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.1 (3H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz, CH₃-C-O), 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃-C=C), 3.51 (2H, q, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₂-O-C), 3.7 (3H, s, methoxy protons), 4.0 (2H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, S-CH₂), 4.6 (1H, s, methine proton), 4.9 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz *cis* allylic proton), 5.1 (1H, d, *J* 16.5 Hz, *trans* allylic proton), 5.5 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchangeable), 5.75 (1H, m, vinylic proton), 6.8–7.2 (4H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) 14.14 (C-CH₂), 33.80 (C=C=C), 52.37 (CH₂-S), 59.71 (CH₂-O), 113.58 (vinylic carbon), 118.00 (vinylic carbon), 127.98, 133.22, 137.05, 158.70 (aromatic carbons), 166.80 (C=O, carbon). HRMS (M⁺) Calcd. : 346; Found : 346.

Selected spectroscopic data for 5b : Elemental analysis : Calcd. : C, 65.03; H, 7.28; N, 8.76(%); Found : C, 65.08; H, 7.21; N, 8.71(%); IR (KBr) 3200 (-NH str.), 1703 cm⁻¹ (C=O str., ester); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.3 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, methyl protons), 2.4 (3H, s, vinylic protons), 2.7 (3H, s, methyl protons), 3.9 (2H, SCH₂ of allyl group), 4.1 (2H, q, *J* 6.8 Hz, OCH₂ of ester), 4.8 (1H, NH, s, D₂O exchangeable), 5.0–5.2 (2H, vinylic protons of allyl group), 5.3 (1H, s, methine proton, N-C-H), 5.7 (1H, m, vinylic proton of allyl group), 6.9–7.3 (4H, m, aromatic protons). HRMS (M⁺) Calcd. : 330; Found : 330.

Selected spectroscopic data for 5c : Elemental analysis : Calcd. : C, 64.12; H, 6.96; N, 8.80(%); Found : C, 64.17; H, 6.92; N, 8.76(%); IR (KBr) 3307 (-NH str.), 1650 (C=O str., ester), 1476 cm⁻¹ (C=C, aliphatic); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.2 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, methyl protons), 2.4 (3H, s, vinylic protons), 3.9 (2H, SCH₂ of allyl group), 4.1 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, OCH₂ of ester), 4.7 (1H, NH, s, D₂O exchangeable), 5.1 (1H, s, methine proton, N-C-H), 5.2–5.3 (2H, vinylic protons of allyl group), 5.9 (1H, m, vinylic proton of allyl group), 6.8–7.2 (5H, m, aromatic protons). HRMS (M⁺) Calcd. : 316; Found : 316.

Selected spectroscopic data for 5d : Elemental analysis : Calcd. : C, 67.98; H, 6.71; N, 9.33(%); Found : C, 67.91; H, 6.78; N, 9.35(%); IR (KBr) 3211 (-NH str.), 1685 cm⁻¹ (C=O str., ester); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.1 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, methyl protons), 1.7 (1H, NH, s, D₂O exchangeable), 2.4 (3H, s, vinylic protons), 4.0 (2H, q, *J* 6.8 Hz, OCH₂ of ester), 4.3 (2H, OCH₂ of allyl group), 5.0–5.2 (2H, vinylic protons of allyl group), 5.3 (1H, s, methine proton, N–C–H), 5.7–5.8 (1H, m, vinylic proton of allyl group), 7.2 (5H, m, aromatic protons); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) 14.43 (C–CH₂), 33.80 (C–C=C), 52.37 (CH₂–S), 59.71 (CH₂–O), 116.58 (vinylic carbon), 118.30 (vinylic carbon), 126.61, 127.68, 128.72, 132.05, 134.2 (aromatic carbons), 153.8 (C=N), 164.40 (C=O, carbon). HRMS (M⁺) Calcd. : 300; Found : 300.

Selected spectroscopic data for 5e : Elemental analysis : Calcd. : C, 68.33; H, 7.65; N, 8.85(%); Found : C, 68.28; H, 7.69; N, 8.89(%); IR (KBr) 3435 (-NH str.), 1692 cm⁻¹ (C=O str., ester); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.2 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, methyl protons), 2.3 (3H, s, vinylic protons), 2.9 (3H, s, methyl protons), 3.8 (2H, q, *J* 6.8 Hz, OCH₂ of ester), 4.1 (2H, OCH₂ of allyl group), 4.7 (1H, NH, s, D₂O exchangeable), 4.9–5.1 (2H, vinylic protons of allyl group), 5.3 (1H, s, methine proton, N–C–H), 5.6 (1H, m, vinylic proton of allyl group), 7.3–8.0 (4H, m, aromatic protons). HRMS (M⁺) Calcd. : 314; Found : 314.

Selected spectroscopic data for 5f : Elemental analysis : Calcd. : C, 65.04; H, 7.28; N, 8.43(%); Found : C, 65.11; H, 7.23; N, 8.46(%); IR (KBr) 3413 (-NH str.), 1697 cm⁻¹ (C=O str., ester); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.1 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, methyl protons), 2.2 (3H, s, vinylic protons), 3.5 (3H, s, methoxy protons), 4.1 (2H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz, OCH₂ of ester), 4.3 (2H, OCH₂ of allyl group), 4.9 (1H, NH, s, D₂O exchangeable), 5.0–5.2 (2H, vinylic protons of allyl group), 5.4 (1H, s, methine proton, N–C–H), 5.7 (1H, m, vinylic proton of allyl group), 7.1–7.6 (4H, m, aromatic protons). HRMS (M⁺) Calcd. : 330; Found : 330.

Selected spectroscopic data of *N*-allyl dihydropyrimidone intermediate of 4a :

IR (KBr) 3413 (-NH str.), 2926 (CH str.), 1697 (C=O str., ester), 1658 (C=O str., imide), 1232 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.2 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₃–C–O), 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃–C=C), 3.51 (2H, q, *J* 6.4 Hz, CH₂–O–C), 3.7 (3H, s, methoxy protons), 4.2 (2H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, N–CH₂), 4.75 (1H, s, methine proton), 5.1 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, *cis* allylic proton), 5.2 (1H, d, *J* 14.6 Hz *trans* allylic proton), 5.6 (1H, m, vinylic proton),

5.82 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchangeable) 6.7–7.1 (4H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) 14.26 (C–CH₂), 34.01 (C–C=C), 55.11 (CH₂–N), 59.60 (CH₂–O), 112.38 (vinylic carbon), 118.51 (vinylic carbon), 128.49, 133.62, 137.51, 154.70 (aromatic carbons), 160.77 (C=S, carbon), 166.95 (C=O, carbon). HRMS (M⁺) Calcd. : 346; Found : 346.

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- Supplementary data for X-ray crystallographic studies of 5a including tables of bond lengths and angles have been deposited with the Director of X-Ray Crystallographic Database, Cambridge and available upon request for 5a CCDC 65793.